

Highlights

- Particles of different composition are deposited on roadside moss samples.
- Washing step is mandatory to study the bioconcentration of PAHs in moss tissue.
- SEM-EDS allows to check the effectiveness in the removal of particles from sample.
- High molecular weight PAHs might be efficiently bioconcentrated in moss tissue.

1 **Sample pretreatment to differentiate between bioconcentration and**
2 **atmospheric deposition of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons in mosses.**
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7
8 **Abstract**

9 In this first approach a comparison using different sample pretreatment methodologies has
10 been made to differentiate between total atmospheric deposition and bioconcentration of
11 polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) in moss samples (*Brachythecium rutabulum*).
12 Samples were collected in a densely polluted urban area in Barakaldo (Biscay, Basque
13 Country) and submitted to different cleaning procedures with the aim to remove as many
14 deposited atmospheric particles as possible. Analysis by means of Scanning Electron
15 Microscopy coupled to Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy (SEM-EDS) allowed to quantify the
16 removal efficiency of each cleaning procedure and to chemically characterise particles still
17 present in the pre-cleaned sample. Cleaning moss samples twice with deionised water in an
18 ultrasound bath showed up as the most suitable way to remove solid particles deposited on
19 their surface. Discerning between bioconcentration and atmospheric deposition is therefore
20 possible after GC-MS quantitative analysis of non-washed and washed moss samples.

21
22 **Keywords:** moss; atmosphere; bioconcentration; SEM; PAH.

23
24 **1. Introduction**

25 Vegetation samples, like mosses and lichens, have been widely used to monitor and identify
26 the sources of a wide range of pollutants like heavy metals (eg. Fernández et al., 2004;
27 Giordano et al., 2005; Anicic et al., 2009) and persistent organic pollutants (POPs) (Blasco et
28 al., 2006; Gerdol et al., 2002; Ötvös et al., 2004). Recent studies have started wondering if the
29 cleaning step prior to the analysis of these samples should be carried out or not (Aboal et al.,
30 2011; Spagnuolo et al., 2013). Still, these studies have only taken into account the effects of
31 the washing step when determining heavy metals but not POPs. Since moss tissues have
32 shown to retain atmospherically deposited polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) as

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33 efficiently as trace metals (Milukaite, 1998), a larger research including the effects of the
34 cleaning step during the analysis of POPs in moss and lichens is required.
35 As stated by Harmens et al (2008), when determining metallic deposition, samples should not
36 be washed. On the other hand, if the aim is to determine the bioconcentration of pollutants in
37 these organisms and the related toxicity, samples should be free of any deposited particle and,
38 therefore, cleaned prior to analysis. However, special care must be taken when washing
39 vegetation samples in order to avoid any kind of contamination and/or non-desired extraction
40 of the analytes from the matrix. Here, once again, only information for heavy metals has been
41 reported (Pérez-Llamazares et al., 2011; Sentenac and Grignon, 1981; Spagnuolo et al., 2013).
42 Regarding the analytes to be studied in this work, PAHs are a large group of organic
43 compounds with two or more fused aromatic rings. Most of the PAHs with low vapour
44 pressure in the air are adsorbed on particles, and as they are highly lipophilic chemicals, they
45 have a relatively low solubility in water (Bjorseth and Ramdahl, 1985). Therefore, fewer
46 problems are to be expected during the washing procedure when using water or other polar
47 solvents compared to the case of heavy metals.
48 In this study mosses (*Brachythecium rutabulum*) were collected in a densely polluted urban
49 area near a highway in Barakaldo (Biscay, Basque Country) and were submitted to different
50 cleaning procedures before analysing them by means of Scanning Electron Microscopy
51 coupled to Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy (SEM-EDS) to i) study the effectiveness of each
52 procedure to remove solid particles deposited on the surface of the sample, ii) characterise the
53 different particles observed in the sample and iii) select the most appropriate pretreatment to
54 discern between deposited and bioconcentrated organic pollution in moss samples. Washed
55 (using the selected cleaning procedure) and non-washed samples were further analysed by
56 Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectroscopy (GC-MS) to investigate the differences in PAH
57 concentrations.

58

59 **2. Materials and Methods**

60 **2.1. Sampling**

61 • The moss species *Brachythecium rutabulum* (Hewd.) Schimp was selected for this study based
62 on its abundance in the sampling area and not on its usage for biomonitoring studies in the
63 surroundings as this was only a first approach to study the aforementioned hypothesis. Still, it
64 has been reported to act as a good bioindicator in the literature (Ötvös et al., 2003; Samecka-
65 Cymerman et al., 2009; Spirić et al., 2014) as it occurs in a wide range of habitats, and is
66 especially common on wood and stones.

67 Moss samples were collected in a densely populated urban area near a heavy traffic area
68 (Diputación Foral de Bizkaia, 2012) including a motorway (A-8, 78,000 vehicles day⁻¹) and
69 two highroads (N-634 and N-637 with 10,000 and 134,000 vehicles day⁻¹, respectively) in
70 Barakaldo (Biscay, Basque Country). The collection of samples was carried out in November
71 2011 after several days without rain in order to obtain the largest amount of deposited
72 particles as possible on the sample. Samples were collected in an area of 20 m² using a scalpel
73 and stored in plastic zipper bags inside portable coolers at low temperature for their
74 transportation to the laboratory. Special care was taken to only collect mosses located on
75 asphalt or cement, but not on soil, to avoid possible blending between soil particles and moss
76 tissues during sample transport.

77

78 **2.2. Cleaning procedures**

79 In the laboratory samples were mixed to further separate them into 8 subsamples. In each
80 subsample the apical segments (10-30 mm long) were cut from moss shoots and 20-30 of
81 them were stored inside glass flasks. 7 different cleaning procedures (Table 1) were proposed
82 with the aim of removing as many particles as possible from the surface of the sample. 6
83 subsamples were submitted to a combination of magnetic stirring or sonication (400 W,
84 ultrasonic bath, JP Selecta) together with 10 mL of Milli-Q water (Millipore, Carrigtwohill,
85 Ireland) or acidified water (HNO₃ 10%, Tracepur grade, Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) for
86 different time lengths as mentioned elsewhere (Spagnuolo et al., 2013). Another subsample
87 was put under a 0.15 bar stream of N₂ (99,9992%, Carbueros Metálicos, Spain) as suggested
88 by Ducceschi et al (1999), holding each shoot individually with tweezers to allow it face the
89 stream from every direction. The remaining subsample was not cleaned and was treated as a
90 control.

91 One of the major drawbacks when dealing with bryophytes and heavy metals consists on the
92 length of the washing step (Sentenac and Grignon, 1981; Wells and Brown, 1990), as
93 procedures of more than 30 s may alter the equilibrium of the extracellular cations. However,
94 when dealing with non-polar organic compounds such as PAHs, the risk of changing this
95 equilibrium does not end up being critical as the octanol-water partition coefficients (K_{ow}) for
96 these organic molecules are rather high. Therefore, the chosen times for both sonication and
97 agitation were considerably higher in some cases.

98

99 **2.3. Scanning Electron Microscopy-Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy (SEM-EDS)**

100 Prior to SEM-EDS analysis of the 8 subsamples, the already cleaned apical segments were
101 dried in an oven at 50°C (it has to be borne in mind that during the drying of samples some of
102 the particles could be detached from the surface). Subsequently, subsamples were carefully
103 mounted on an aluminium stub and coated with graphite.

104 Particles deposited on both abaxial and adaxial surfaces of the samples were observed at
105 ambient temperature using a scanning electron microscope (Carl Zeiss AG, EVO 40,
106 Oberkochen, Germany) equipped with an energy dispersive spectrometer (SDD X-max 50,
107 Oxford Instruments, Abingdom, UK). SEM observations were carried out at magnifications up
108 to 2000x approximately, while the electron beam energy was fixed at about 20 eV, being the
109 working distance in most of the cases 10 mm and the probe current of 100 pA. Particles were
110 observed as backscattered electron images and further subdivided in three size classes (<2.5
111 µm, 2.5–10 µm and >10µm in maximum diameter) for their quantification using an image
112 editing software (Adobe Photoshop CS5).

113

114 **2.4. PAHs determination in moss**

115 The concentrations of 16 selected PAHs were measured in washed (using the proposed
116 procedure) and non-washed moss samples. Samples were freeze dried in a Cryodos apparatus
117 (48 h, -52.2 °C, $5.4 \cdot 10^{-2}$ mbar; Telstar, Spain) before analysis. All solvents used were of
118 HPLC grade and were obtained from Lab-Scan (Gliwice, Poland). Approximately 1.5g of
119 dried moss were accurately weighed in a Mettler AJ150 analytical balance (Mettler Toledo,
120 Spain) and submitted to Microwave Assisted Extraction (MAE) together with a mixture of 20
121 mL of acetone:n-hexane (1:1) and 20 µL of deuterated PAH (S-4124 deuterated PAH mixture,
122 Chiron AS. Trondheim, Norway) used as surrogate. The extraction conditions in the
123 microwave (MarsXpress, CEM, Kamp-Lintfort, Germany) were as follows: for the first 5
124 minutes, the system was allowed to reach 120°C using full power (100%, 1600 W); in the
125 next 10 minutes, the temperature previously reached was kept constant. The extracts were
126 filtered through Millex[®] HV0.45 µm PVDF filters (Millipore, Carrigtwohill, Ireland) and then
127 concentrated to 1 mL using a gentle stream of nitrogen in a TurboVap LV Evaporator
128 (Zymark, Hopkinton, MA, USA) at 35 °C. A clean-up step was carried out by Solid Phase
129 Extraction (SPE) with 2g Florisil[®] cartridges (purchased from Supelco) previously
130 conditioned with 10 mL of n-hexane. Analytes were eluted with 14 mL of a mixture of n-
131 hexane:toluene 65:35 (v:v). Subsequently, the extract was evaporated to dryness, re-dissolved
132 in 100 µL of n-hexane and kept in dark at -18°C until GC-MS analysis according to the
133 procedure described elsewhere (Bustamante et al., 2010).

134

135 **3. Results and discussion**

136 **3.1. Cleaning efficiency**

137 A selection of the most representative SEM images obtained for all the subsamples after
138 going through the different cleaning procedures are shown in Fig.1.

139 Dry deposition depends on physical characteristics of the particles (such as size and shape),
140 the meteorological conditions (wind speed, thermal stability...), and morphological
141 characteristics of the biological surface (Tomasevic et al., 2005). The quantification of the
142 total amount of particles in all the obtained microphotographs and taking average values for
143 each washing method led us to the next most important conclusions: as expected, subsamples
144 subjected to different cleaning procedures show different amounts of remaining particles (b,
145 21; c, 44; d, 5; e, 5; f, 29; g, 31; h, 76; on average) but always less compared to the unwashed
146 one (a, 91; on average). Procedures may be sorted according to their efficiency to remove
147 particles (from lower to higher efficiency) as follows: $h \ll c \sim b < g \sim f < d \sim e$.

148 The use of a controlled stream of dry nitrogen (h) allowed the elimination of the largest
149 particles ($>10 \mu\text{m}$) without damaging the structure of the matrix; however, like in the case of
150 agitation (b and c), it resulted in an inefficient technique for the cleaning the smallest particles
151 (<2.5 and $2.5\text{-}10 \mu\text{m}$) on the samples (h, 72.4% and 27.6%; b, 72.7% and 18.2%; c, 70.4%
152 and 25%, respectively). The ultrasonic bath assisted cleaning appeared to be the best way to
153 obtain a particle-free surface (microphotographs d, e, f and g). Moreover, repeating the
154 cleaning procedure twice (2x15 min) was more efficient than a single ultrasound run,
155 regardless of using nitric acid or milliQ water, (microphotographs d and e vs. f and g).
156 However, as the differences between d) and e) were not important and considering other
157 factors like ease of use, safety and that H_2O is less aggressive than HNO_3 , we recommend to
158 clean moss samples twice with deionised water in an ultrasound bath as the most suitable way
159 to remove solid particles deposited on their surface. It has to be considered that these results
160 might vary between species and direct extrapolations are to be avoided.

161

162 **3.2. Characterisation of the particles**

163 The potential of the SEM-EDS technique to characterise solid particles present in the surface
164 of vegetation samples like moss using the elemental information provided in the
165 corresponding XRF spectra was also tested. Several particles (found in a wide range of
166 diameters up to $10 \mu\text{m}$) in the microphotographs were randomly selected, and their XRF

167 spectra was measured. The chemical elements identified in the particles were C, O, Na, Cl,
168 Mg, Al, Si, P, S, K, Ca, Fe and Zn, being C, O, Si, Ca and Al the most abundant ones (Fig. 2).
169 Depending on their chemical composition, two categories of particles were observed: particles
170 of biological sources such as those coming from moss itself, soot and pollen (Fig. 2. a, b and
171 c), and particles coming from the re-deposition of atmospheric dust (Fig. 2. d, e and f). The
172 particle in Fig. 2a was identified as part of the moss subsample as its spectra showed no
173 difference compared to other studied areas in clean moss subsamples (C:O proportion 70:20,
174 approximately). Therefore, this spectrum was treated as a blank when studying other foreign
175 particles in moss subsamples.

176 Different chemical ratios were found in other subsamples. In Fig. 2b, a major abundance of C
177 was observed compared to the moss blank spectrum (Fig. 2a), suggesting the presence of soot,
178 an organic material typically found in the environment due to the incomplete combustion of
179 wood or coal and a potential source of PAHs. Fig. 2c showed a similar spectrum to the blank
180 one, slightly varying the proportion between C and O. This new particle, due to its form and
181 composition, seemed to be a pollen particle, with a size of about 10 μm , and clearly differed
182 from the previously studied soot particle.

183 Studying particles coming from the re-deposition of atmospheric dust, the presence of Ca in
184 Fig. 2d was really notorious. This may suggest the presence of CaCO_3 in the particles
185 attached to the moss samples, due to their proximity to the soil. Moreover, the spectrum in Fig
186 2e, indicates the presence, among others, of Al, Si and Fe. This kind of chemical elements can
187 form diverse chemical structures, such as iron oxides and aluminosilicates.

188 Additionally, a glass particle was found in Fig. 2f, surely made up by Si, CaCO_3 and Na_2CO_3 .
189 It is important to highlight the presence of Mg in this microphotograph, as Mg can be used as
190 an additive for colouring glass.

191

192 **3.3. Deposition vs. bioconcentration**

193 16 PAHs were analysed in two moss subsamples. One of them was washed using the chosen
194 cleaning procedure (Table 1, procedure 4). The other one was directly analysed, without any
195 prior cleaning procedure. The results are shown in Fig. 3. The already washed subsample was
196 subjected to a second cleaning cycle in order to assure that the effects of the ultrasonic energy,
197 using deionised water in the cleaning process, were not significant concerning the extraction
198 of the bioconcentrated analytes in mosses ($\alpha=0.05$, $n=3$).

199 As it can be observed, concentrations of most of the PAHs were lower in the previously
200 washed subsample. However, in analytes like acenaphthylene and the heaviest compounds

201 such as benzo[k]fluoranthene, indeno[1,2,3-cd]pyrene, dibenz[ah]anthracene and
202 benzo[ghi]perylene, no difference could be observed between the washed and non-washed
203 subsamples ($\alpha=0.05$). This fact suggests that even if this kind of compounds is mainly found
204 associated to particles rather than to the gas phase, they can be easily bioconcentrated in the
205 moss tissue.

206 PAH concentration in mosses and in particles attached to their surface has been previously
207 reported to be related to the emission source (Ares et al., 2009; Augusto et al., 2009). In this
208 case, mosses were collected close to a densely populated urban area near a heavy traffic area.
209 Thus, a strong connection between these sources and the concentration of PAHs in both
210 washed and non-washed samples was to be expected. Ratios between specific compounds,
211 such as B[a]A/(B[a]A + Cry) and B[a]P/B[ghi]P have been proposed as valuable source
212 indicators of traffic related sources for PAHs (Tobiszewski and Namiesnik, 2012). The results
213 in this study, even though they are not representative, show a clear connection with traffic
214 related sources not only in the case of non-washed mosses (B[a]A/(B[a]A + Cry) = 0.48;
215 >0.35, vehicular emission; and B[a]P/B[ghi]P = 0.62; >0.6, traffic emission), but also in the
216 case of the washed ones (B[a]A/(B[a]A + Cry) = 0.51; >0.35, vehicular emission), suggesting
217 a potential link between the source of the PAHs found in particles attached to mosses and of
218 those bioconcentrated in their tissues.

219

220 **4. Conclusions**

221 This preliminary research confirms that mosses may act as good sentinels of atmospheric
222 pollution caused by PAHs. However, an appropriate sample pretreatment must be selected
223 depending on the aim of the work. For the specie under analysis a previous washing step
224 using ultrasonic energy and deionised water is mandatory if the objective is to remove as
225 many attached particles as possible and to study the bioconcentration of PAHs in moss tissue.
226 Still, a deeper research is necessary including other moss species and different sampling areas
227 to reaffirm this statement.

228 During this approach SEM-EDS has been confirmed to be an attractive alternative to check
229 the effectiveness in the removal of particles from the surface of the sample using different
230 cleaning procedures. This technique also entails the characterisation of the particles present in
231 the sample, which helps to identify the presence of potentially interfering moles (i.e. soot) in
232 the analysis of PAHs. Finally, even though this observation deserves further investigation, the
233 results obtained here suggest that i) high molecular weight PAHs could be efficiently
234 bioconcentrated in moss tissue even if they are primarily adsorbed in atmospheric particles

235 rather than in gas phase and ii) there might be a potential link between the source of the PAHs
236 found in particles attached to mosses and that of PAHs bioaccumulated in their tissues.

237

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243

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1 **Tables**

2

3 **Table 1.** Different cleaning procedures proposed for the 8 moss subsamples.

Subsample	Cleaning procedure	Time (min)
1	No cleaning	-
2	HNO ₃ (10%) + agitation	240
3	Milli-Q water + agitation	240
4	Milli-Q water + ultrasonic bath	2x (15)
5	HNO ₃ (10%) + ultrasonic bath	2x (15)
6	Milli-Q water + ultrasonic bath	15
7	HNO ₃ (10%) + ultrasonic bath	15
8	Stream of N ₂	5

4

5

Figure 1
[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

a

e

b

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c

g

d

h

Figure 2
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a

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c

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Figure 3
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1 **Figure captions**

2

3 **Fig. 1.** Microphotographs showing particles on the surface of the unwashed moss subsample a) and the
4 washed moss subsamples: b) 10% HNO₃ + agitation (240 min); c) H₂O + agitation (240 min); d) H₂O
5 + USB (15 min x2); e) 10% HNO₃ + USB (15 min x2); f) H₂O + USB (15 min); g) 10% HNO₃ + USB
6 (15 min); h) N₂stream).

7

8 **Fig. 2.** XRF spectra of particles present in moss subsamples. The particle corresponding to each
9 spectrum is indicated inside a black/white circle.

10

11 **Fig. 3.** Concentrations (ng g⁻¹) of 16 PAHs including Naphthalene, Nap; Acenaphthylene, Acy;
12 Acenaphthene, Ace; Fluorene, Flu; Phenanthrene, Phe; Anthracene, Ant; Fluoranthene, Flr; Pyrene,
13 Pyr; Benz[a]anthracene, B[a]A; Chrysene, Cry; Benzo[b]fluoranthene, B[b]F; Benzo[k]fluoranthene,
14 B[k]F; Benzo[a]pyrene; B[a]P; Indeno[1,2,3-cd]pyrene, Ind; Dibenz[ah]anthracene, D[ah]A and
15 Benzo[ghi]perylene, B[ghi]P found in a non-washed moss subsample and in a subsample subjected to
16 the cleaning procedure recommended in this work (n=3).

17

